

ANALYSIS OF THE STRATEGIC SITUATION OF STEKLOPLASTIK MJCH IN THE MARKET

Musyeva Shaira Azimovna

Samarkand Institute of Economy and Service

Professor of Marketing department

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Abstract. *In this article, the use of the SWOT analysis method, product quality, product production and sales results, strategic planning stages, which is widely used in strategic marketing, is considered in the evaluation and analysis of the company's strategic situation in the furniture market of the republic.*

Keywords: *enterprise, furniture products, strategy, analysis, market, demand, offer.*

Introduction. The furniture and woodworking industry of Uzbekistan is one of the rapidly developing industries in our country. If 5-8 years ago, 65-70% of the domestic market of our country was made up of products of foreign manufacturers, today about 90% of the market capacity is satisfied with high-quality domestic products. More than 1,100 furniture production and assembly enterprises operate in the republic, 500 of them are established in Tashkent. Furniture production enterprises are of great importance in meeting the daily needs of the people of our country and in creating decent living conditions in residential areas. Furniture is needed for any new home or social facility, so as the economy develops, the demand for furniture will increase. As an example, we will give the figures for the end of 2022.

At the end of the year, the total area in our country is 12,078.1 thousand square meters. residences have been built and commissioned. We should take into account that all this is equipped with kitchen, bedroom, soft and other types of furniture. In January-December 2022, 311,400 marriages were registered by the registry office, which means certain furniture will be purchased for so many new families. Analyzing the development of the social sphere, modern hospitals with 6,032 beds, polyclinics with 19,368 visits, general education and specialized schools with 77,436 student places were built during the year. Each built object requires specialized furniture. In addition, it is possible to have an idea about part of the demand for furniture, taking into account the construction of capital renovated facilities, various office and administrative facilities.

Analysis of literature on the topic. Based on foreign experiences, it should be noted that many economists have been engaged in the development of marketing principles and their practical application. Among them, we can include famous scientists such as F. Kotler, M. Porter, D. Evans, I. Ansoff, M. Berman, M. Golubkov, P. Samuelson, D. Marshall.

It is necessary to acknowledge the scientists who made a great contribution to the development of the marketing theory in the economy, while the researches conducted in the field of marketing in our country for many years are based on national characteristics. These include M. Mukhammedov, M. Pardaev, R. Ibragimov, Y. Abdullaev, A. Saliev, M. Sharifkhojaev, B. Khodiev, D. Rakhimova, R. Boltaboev, D. Ergashkhodjaeva and others can be included.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results The production process of furniture production is a set of all processes related to the transformation of raw materials and materials entering the enterprise into

finished products. It includes the direct impact of machines, tools and labor on the raw materials and materials from which the product is made. The main stages of the technological process of furniture production are drying wood, cutting it, processing rough blanks, gluing and veneering them, processing finished blanks, assembling parts into units, assembly of processing units, finishing aggregates and parts and is to collect them. product.

Currently, the main activity of JSC "Stekloplastik" is directed to the provision of specialized furniture and sports equipment to general education, pre-school education and medical institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The enterprise produces specialized furniture and sports equipment in a range of more than 180 names, including:

- More than 60 items of furniture;
- Furniture of educational institutions up to 20 names;
- More than 20 medical furniture;
- sports equipment of more than 50 names;
- Over 30 items of office and household furniture;
- several other products made of glass-plastic materials.

The main customers of JSC "Stekloplastik" are the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Special Vocational Education Center of the Ministry of Higher and Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, engineering companies under regional authorities, and the foreign economic company "Uzmedeksport". "Stekloplastik" OJSC started the production of furniture based on the tenders announced by the Asian Bank under the education development program.

Since 70% of the raw materials used in the production activities of JSC "Stekloplastik" are obtained from local production enterprises, the price of the product is reasonable for consumers and is much cheaper compared to imported products. The quality of the product manufactured by the enterprise is confirmed by quality certificates and 14 patents of the standardization and metrology center of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In addition, Stekloplastik OJSC has implemented a quality management system in accordance with ISO 9001:2000 international standards.

Today, the cocktail team at "Stekloplastik" OJSC is about 300 people, most of them are highly qualified specialists. The average monthly salary of workers is 2740 thousand soums.

"Stekloplastik" OJSC has an active policy in the household furniture market. In 2005-2006, as a result of organizing the production of new types of office and household furniture, more than 20 jobs were created and sales volume increased. Today, such furniture is delivered to buyers on the basis of consumer credit.

In recent years, in order to improve the production, the company purchased and put into operation a number of special equipment and technological lines produced in foreign countries. These include TURANLAR (Turkey), YING LING Machinery (Taiwan), eRMAKSAN (Turkey), and some Chinese equipment. The development of these devices helps to improve the operations and, therefore, to increase the quality of the product.

In recent years, JSC "Stekloplastik" has managed to equip more than 1,000 pre-school educational institutions, schools, academic lyceums and vocational colleges, universities with high-quality modern furniture.

The total area of the enterprise is 13.2 hectares. The area of production buildings is 2.4 hectares. The enterprise employs 252 people.

The volume of products produced in 2021 was 68.1 billion soums or 6 million soums, 190 thousand US dollars.

The main activities of the enterprise include:

- fiberglass products
- Medical furniture and equipment
- sports equipment and equipment
- Specialized furniture for educational institutions
- Office furniture
- Metal products

We can see the production activity of "Stekloplastik" LLC in 2022 in the following table and diagram. (Table 1)

Table 1

Results of product production and sales at Stekloplastik LLC in 2022

Tr	Product types	Amount, billion soums	Contribution, %
1	Medical equipment	7800	8
2	Special laboratory equipment	6700	6
3	Sports equipment	3300	3
4	Study and office furniture	28300	27
5	Glass plastic products	21000	20
6	Playground and workout	14200	14
7	Metal products	4200	4
8	Children's furniture	18500	18

The following table presents the comparative data of the production activity of "Stekloplastik" LLC in 2021-2022.

Table 2

Changes in the volume of products produced at Stekloplastik LLC in 2021-2022

No	Product nomenclature	2021		2022	
		Number	Amount, million soums	Number	Amount, million soums
1	Medical equipment	13467	7230	20822	7800
2	Special laboratory equipment	54496	5860	76478	6700
3	Sports equipment	540	2500	537	3300

4	Study and office furniture	6179	2640	6260	28300
5	Glass plastic products	250	18540	1203	21000
6	Playground and workout	220344	136	191232	14200
7	Metal products	136526	2200	124724	4200
8	Children's furniture	144450	14680	158847	18500
	Total	576252	53726	580103	104000

Figure 2. Production dynamics of Stekloplastik LLC in 2021-2022

It can be seen from this diagram that the production of the main groups of the product range of "Stekloplastik" LLC was uneven. For example, the production of educational and office furniture has increased sharply, while children's furniture has remained almost unchanged. The group of playground and workout furniture can be called the discovery of 2021, because its production has increased a lot.

Based on the general information, let's evaluate the strategic situation of the enterprise in the furniture market of the republic. We will use the SWOT analysis method, which is widely used

in strategic marketing, to analyze the situation and position of "Stekloplastik" LLC. In this method, we enter the strengths and weaknesses, opportunities and threats of the enterprise into a two-dimensional matrix and analyze them. (-table)

Table 3.

Analysis of strengths and weaknesses of STEKLOPLASTIK LLC

Strengths (S)	Weaknesses (W)
Technological specialization; Orientation to a specific segment of the market; Many years of experience; Highly qualified personnel;	Low percentage of new equipment; Service to legal entities only; Assortment updates are slow; Not actively acting against competitors; Financial problems
Opportunities (O)	Risks (T)
Support of the industry by the state; Increase in the size of investment programs; Introduction of furniture making technologies	The rate of change of fashions in the special furniture market; Changes in the composition of consumers; Increase of new competitors; Change in office technology.

As can be seen from the table, the specialization of "Stekloplastik" LLC in the market of luxury furniture substantiates its strengths and expands its capabilities. At the same time, the limitation of technologies and the deep specialization of the assortment creates risks for the enterprise.

As a result of a comprehensive study of the influence of SWOT factors, a general conclusion is drawn on the main options of the marketing strategy. (-table)

Table 4.

Matrix of marketing strategies chosen by "STEKLOPLASTIK" LLC based on SWOT analysis

	Strong	Weak
Opportunity	An opportunity-based strengths development strategy	Strategies to overcome weaknesses based on capabilities
Danger	A strategy for leveraging strengths against risk	A strategy to avoid risk, move to another segment

This table shows the attractive marketing strategies used by "Stekloplastik" LLC according to the results of the SWOT analysis.

All of the four mentioned strategies are suitable for use by "Stekloplastik" LLC, but several conditions must be met for their implementation. That is why we consider it necessary to name the company's range of products. The first method of analysis is to construct a BCG matrix (5-table)

According to the analysis of the BCG-matrix, two types of products are included in the "question marks" of the assortment of "Stekloplastik" LLC, that is, bus spare parts and workout equipment, special laboratory equipment for "stars", children's furniture, playground and glass plastic products. "Milk cows" include the following products: medical equipment, educational, office furniture, swimming pools, boats and water attractions. Among the products, low profit and unstable demand include plastic products, sports equipment and metal products.

In conclusion, Internal factors affecting the value of "Stekloplastik" LLC, the enterprise itself has a positive opportunity for its own benefit. External factors directly affect the value of the

enterprise under the influence of the government and the market. For this, the enterprise itself must adapt to the external environment. The conducted theoretical and practical researches are dedicated to the modern trends of marketing strategy and are carried out on the example of "Stekloplastik" LLC. The results of research are the basis for the following conclusions.

Table 5

Analysis of the assortment of "STEKLOPLASTIK" LLC based on the "Boston Consulting Group" matrix

"The Stars"	"Milky Cows"
Special laboratory equipment Children's furniture Playground Glass plastic products	Medical equipment Educational, office furniture swimming pools, Boats and water attractions
Bus spare parts Workout	Plastic products Sports equipment Metal products
"Question Mark"	"Dogs"

Scientific and methodological research in modern marketing theory practically shows the priority of strategic thinking in this discipline. The continuous improvement of strategic marketing methods and approaches within the science is the basis for new methods and processes in today's marketing. One of these is the methodology of strategic analysis.

The development of marketing in industrial enterprises leads to the formation of a strategic marketing system in management. It is possible to demonstrate the application of strategic planning stages, the use of strategic marketing principles, and the organization of strategic analysis departments.

Creating a marketing strategy requires the use of specific analytical methods in enterprises. One of the directions of these methods is the matrix analysis method. The essence of this method is that all analyzed indicators and factors are brought into the form of a matrix. These methods include PESTEL analysis, SWOT-analysis, strategic map of competitors, BKG matrix and others. Each used matrix has its own meaning in the strategic analysis of the enterprise.

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